

Model for Improving Students' Professional Competencies Basing on Motivational Learning Approach

Mahzuna ALIBEKOVA¹

Gulistan State University

ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received October 2024

Received in revised form 5

November 2024

Accepted 15 November 2024

Available online

26 November 2024

Keywords:

professional competencies, motivational learning, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, Self-Determination Theory, growth mindset, active learning, collaborative learning, autonomy.

ABSTRACT

In today's competitive and dynamic workplace, professional competencies are crucial for career success. In the context of higher education, these competencies encompass the knowledge, skills, and behaviors essential for effective performance in professional settings. As educational systems strive to prepare students for real-world challenges, the motivational learning approach offers an innovative method to enhance the development of these competencies. By leveraging both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, educators can create environments that promote deeper engagement and mastery of key skills. This article presents a model for improving professional competencies through a motivational learning framework, incorporating principles such as autonomy support, mastery goals, and social learning. The model outlines four interconnected phases – Preparation, Engagement, Reflection, and Integration – designed to foster continuous development, feedback, and application of competencies in real-world contexts. Ultimately, this approach encourages students to embrace a growth mindset, engage in self-directed learning, and successfully transition from academic learning to professional practice, better preparing them for the demands of the modern workforce.

2181-3701 / © 2024 in Science LLC

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-3701-vol2-iss6-pp58-64>

This is an open-access article under the Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/deed.ru>)

¹ PhD Student, Gulistan State University. E-mail: alibekova_mahzuna@gmail.com

Motivatsion ta'lim yondashuvi asosida talabalarning kasbiy kompetentsiyalarni takomillashtirishning modeli

Keywords:

kasbiy kompetensiyalar, motivatsion ta'lim, ichki motivatsiya, tashqi motivatsiya, o'z-o'zini aniqlash nazariyasi, o'sish tafakkuri, faol o'rganish, hamkorlikda o'rganish, avtonomiya.

ANNOTATSIYA

Bugungi raqobatbardosh va dinamik ish joyida professional kompetensiyalar martaba muvaffaqiyati uchun juda muhimdir. Oliy ta'lim kontekstida bu kompetensiyalar kasbiy sharoitlarda samarali ishlash uchun zarur bo'lgan bilim, ko'nikma va xulq-atvorni o'z ichiga oladi. Ta'lim tizimlari o'quvchilarni haqiqiy dunyo muammolariga tayyorlashga intilayotganligi sababli, motivatsion ta'lim yondashuvi ushbu kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirish uchun innovatsion usulni taklif qiladi. Ichki va tashqi motivatsiyadan foydalangan holda, o'qituvchilar chuqurroq ishtirok etish va asosiy ko'nikmalarni egallashga yordam beradigan muhit yaratishi mumkin. Ushbu maqola avtonomiyani qo'llab-quvvatlash, o'zlashtirish maqsadlari va ijtimoiy ta'lim kabi tamoyillarni o'z ichiga olgan motivatsion ta'lim tizimi orqali professional kompetensiyalarni takomillashtirish modelini taqdim etadi. Model bir-biriga bog'langan to'rtta bosqichni – Tayyorgarlik, Ishtirok etish, Mulohaza yuritish va Integratsiyani – belgilaydi va doimiy rivojlanish, fikr-mulohaza yuritish va haqiqiy dunyo kontekstlarida kompetensiyalarni qo'llashni ta'minlash uchun mo'ljallangan. Oxir oqibat, bu yondashuv talabalarni o'sish tafakkurini qabul qilishga, o'z-o'zini yo'naltirilgan ta'limga jalb qilishga va akademik ta'limdan professional amaliyotga muvaffaqiyatli o'tishga, ularni zamonaviy ishchi kuchi talablariga yaxshiroq tayyorlashga undaydi.

Модель совершенствования профессиональных компетенций студентов на основе мотивационного образовательного подхода

Keywords:

профессиональные компетенции, мотивационное обучение, внутренняя мотивация, внешняя мотивация, теория самоопределения, установка на рост, активное обучение, совместное обучение, автономия.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В современных конкурентных и динамичных рабочих условиях профессиональные компетенции имеют решающее значение для карьерного успеха. В контексте высшего образования эти компетенции охватывают знания, навыки и поведение, необходимые для эффективной работы в профессиональной среде. Поскольку образовательные системы стремятся подготовить студентов к реальным вызовам, мотивационный подход к обучению предлагает инновационный метод для улучшения развития этих

компетенций. Используя как внутреннюю, так и внешнюю мотивацию, преподаватели могут создавать среду, способствующую более глубокому вовлечению и овладению ключевыми навыками. В этой статье представлена модель для улучшения профессиональных компетенций с помощью мотивационной структуры обучения, включающей такие принципы, как поддержка автономии, цели овладения и социальное обучение. Модель описывает четыре взаимосвязанных этапа — Подготовка, Вовлечение, Рефлексия и Интеграция — разработанные для содействия непрерывному развитию, обратной связи и применению компетенций в реальных контекстах. В конечном счете, этот подход побуждает студентов принять установку на рост, заниматься самостоятельным обучением и успешно переходить от академического обучения к профессиональной практике, лучше подготавливая их к требованиям современной рабочей силы.

INTRODUCTION

Professional competencies are the backbone of an individual's success in a modern, competitive, and dynamic workplace environment. In the educational context, these competencies refer to the knowledge, skills, and behaviors that students need to acquire in order to perform effectively in their future careers. As higher education systems increasingly emphasize preparing students for real-world challenges, it is essential to explore new methods that improve the development of these competencies. One such method is the motivational learning approach, which leverages motivation to enhance learning outcomes.

Motivation is a critical factor in determining how students engage with and process information, which ultimately affects their development of professional competencies. By tapping into the power of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, educators can create environments that foster deeper learning and greater mastery of skills. This article presents a model for improving students' professional competencies by applying a motivational learning approach, drawing from existing research and theoretical frameworks to design a practical methodology that could be implemented in diverse educational settings.

LITERATURE REVIEW: THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Motivation plays a central role in the educational process [1; 9], guiding the efforts, persistence, and focus that students invest in their learning [7]. Deci and Ryan's Self-Determination Theory (SDT) is foundational in understanding motivation within educational contexts [8]. According to SDT, motivation exists on a continuum from intrinsic motivation (performing an activity for its inherent satisfaction) [2] to extrinsic motivation (performing an activity to achieve a separable outcome) motivation is particularly powerful because it fosters a sense of autonomy, competence, and relatedness – three basic psychological needs identified by SDT [3] that are essential for promoting sustained engagement and effective learning.

In professional competency development, motivation influences how students engage with the curriculum and the learning processes [4] that develop the required competencies. A motivated student is more likely to take initiative, seek additional learning opportunities, and persevere through challenges, all of which contribute to the acquisition of professional skills. Therefore, a motivational learning approach focuses on creating environments that stimulate and maintain students' intrinsic motivation [2] while also leveraging extrinsic motivation when necessary.

PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES IN THE CONTEXT OF HIGHER EDUCATION

Professional competencies encompass a broad range of abilities that are vital for success in the workplace. These include technical skills, soft skills (e.g., communication, teamwork), critical thinking, problem-solving, adaptability, and ethical decision-making. According to the European Qualifications Framework (EQF), professional competencies also encompass the ability to apply knowledge in practical situations, work collaboratively, and demonstrate responsibility and autonomy [9].

In higher education primary challenge is how to ensure that students not only acquire academic knowledge but also develop the skills necessary for professional success. Educators need to design curricula and teaching strategies that actively engage students, provide hands-on experiences, and integrate real-world scenarios that demand critical thinking and problem-solving abilities [6]. Traditional teaching methods, such as lectures and textbooks, often fail to motivate students to engage with learning in a way that promotes the development of these competencies. This is where the motivational learning approach offers a promising alternative.

THE MOTIVATIONAL LEARNING APPROACH: PRINCIPLES AND TECHNIQUES

A motivational learning approach integrates various motivational theories and teaching techniques to foster both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in students. Key principles that underpin this approach include:

1. **Autonomy Support:** Allowing students to make choices in their learning process increases their sense of control and ownership, which boosts intrinsic motivation. Providing opportunities for self-directed learning and individualized projects can enhance students' engagement with their studies and promote critical thinking and creativity.

2. **Mastery Goals:** F mastery rather than performance encourages students to view learning as a process of self-improvement rather than a competition. This orientation helps students embrace challenges, persist through setbacks, and engage deeply with content, all of which contribute to competency development.

3. **Relevance:** Making learning relevant to students' future careers by linking theoretical concepts to real-world applications increases the perceived value of the material. For example, integrating case studies, internships, and practical exercises helps students see the direct applicability of what they are learning to their professional goals.

4. **Feedback and Recognition:** Offering constructive feedback that emphasizes growth and improvement, rather than merely grading, helps students understand their

strengths and areas for development [4]. Celebrating achievements, whether big or small, also fosters motivation by acknowledging students' progress.

5. Social Learning: Collaborative learning environments where students work together on projects or engage in group discussions can enhance motivation by promoting a sense of community and social connectedness. Peer interactions also provide opportunities for feedback and the sharing of different perspectives, which is beneficial for competency development.

6. Growth Mindset: Encouraging students to adopt a growth mindset – the belief that abilities and intelligence can be developed through effort and learning – supports motivation by fostering resilience and persistence in the face of challenges [5].

THE MODEL FOR IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES

The model presented here for improving students' professional competencies integrates the principles of the motivational learning approach into a comprehensive framework. This model consists of four interconnected phases: Preparation, Engagement, Reflection, and Integration. These phases represent a cyclical process that allows for continuous improvement and feedback.

1. Preparation Phase: Setting Clear Goals and Expectations

The first step in the model is to create an environment where students are motivated to succeed. This involves clearly articulating the learning objectives and professional competencies that students are expected to develop. Students should understand the relevance of the curriculum to their future careers, which can be accomplished through presentations, discussions, and guest speakers who can share their real-world experiences. Setting clear, achievable goals provides students with a sense of direction and purpose, helping them stay motivated throughout the learning process. In this phase, educators can also encourage students to set personal learning goals. Self-directed learning, where students take responsibility for identifying areas in which they want to improve, enhances intrinsic motivation by fostering autonomy. Students should also be introduced to strategies for time management, self-regulation, and goal-setting, which are essential professional competencies.

2. Engagement Phase: Active Learning and Collaborative Experiences

The engagement phase focuses on maintaining student interest and involvement in learning activities. This phase is characterized by active learning strategies that emphasize hands-on experiences, problem-solving, and critical thinking. Students should be given opportunities to engage in real-world tasks, such as simulations, case studies, project-based assignments, or internships, that challenge them to apply theoretical knowledge in practice. Collaborative learning is also emphasized in this phase. Working in teams on group projects helps students develop teamwork, communication, and conflict resolution skills – key professional competencies. It also creates an environment where students are motivated to help one another, share knowledge, and learn from peers. Teachers should encourage intrinsic motivation through the use of mastery goals, ensuring that assessments and tasks focus on the learning process rather than just the end result. This approach fosters a deeper understanding of the content, as students are more likely to engage with material when they are not merely focused on grades but on improving their own competencies.

3. Reflection Phase: Feedback and Self-Assessment

The reflection phase is critical in helping students consolidate their learning and develop a deeper understanding of their competencies. It involves self-assessment, peer feedback, and teacher feedback. Reflective activities – such as journaling, group discussions, or one-on-one meetings with educators – allow students to assess their progress, identify strengths and weaknesses, and set new learning goals. Constructive feedback is essential for motivation, as it helps students understand what they are doing well and where they need to improve. Feedback should be specific, actionable, and framed positively to encourage continued effort and improvement. Students should be encouraged to view feedback as an opportunity for growth rather than as a judgment of their abilities.

4. Integration Phase: Applying Competencies in Real-World Contexts

In the integration phase, students are given opportunities to apply their acquired professional competencies in real-world contexts [10]. This might involve internships, service-learning projects, or collaborative industry partnerships. These experiences help students transition from academic learning to professional practice, reinforcing the relevance of their education and providing opportunities for further skill development. Integrating the learned competencies into professional settings fosters a sense of accomplishment and confidence in students, thereby enhancing their intrinsic motivation to continue developing their skills [11]. This phase also provides valuable feedback to the educational institution, as it allows teachers to assess how well students can transfer their learning into practical applications.

CONCLUSION

The model for improving students' professional competencies using a motivational learning approach emphasizes the importance of creating an environment that supports both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. By focusing on autonomy, mastery, relevance, and social learning, educators can foster deeper engagement, critical thinking, and skill development in students. This approach not only enhances students' professional competencies but also prepares them for success in their future careers by encouraging a mindset of continuous learning and self-improvement. The integration of these elements into educational practices represents a promising pathway to better preparing students for the demands of the modern workforce. The adoption of this model can contribute to the development of more motivated, competent, and adaptable graduates who are ready to tackle the complex challenges of the 21st century job market.

REFERENCES:

1. Al-Harthy, I. S. (2016). Contemporary motivation learning theories: a review. *Int. J. Learn. Manag. Syst.* 4, 99–117. doi: 10.18576/ijlms/040205
2. Bieg, S., Beckes, S., and Mittag, W. (2011). The role of intrinsic motivation for teaching, teachers' care and autonomy support in students' self-determined motivation. *J. Educ. Res. Online* 3, 122–140. doi: 10.25656/01:4685
3. Boström, L., and Bostedt, G. (2020). What about study motivation? Students' and teachers' perspectives on what affects study motivation. *Int. J. Learn. Teach. Educ. Res.* 19, 40–59. doi: 10.26803/ijlter.19.8.3

4. Carless, D., and Boud, D. (2018). The development of student feedback literacy: enabling uptake of feedback. *Assess. Eval. High. Educ.* 43, 1315–1325. doi: 10.1080/02602938.2018.1463354
5. Dweck, C. S., and Molden, D. C. (2017). “Mindsets: their impact on competence motivation and acquisition” in *Handbook of competence and motivation: Theory and application*. eds. A. J. Elliot, C. S. Dweck, and D. S. Yeager (New York: The Guilford Press), 135–154.
6. Gopalan, V., Bakar, J. A. A., Zulkifli, A. N., Alwi, A., and Mat, R. C. (2017). A review of the motivation theories in learning. *AIP Conf. Proc.* 1891:20043. doi: 10.1063/1.5005376
7. Makulova, A. T., Alimzhanova, G. M., Bekturganova, Z. M., Umirzakova, Z. A., Makulova, L. T., and Karymbayeva, K. M. (2015). Theory and practice of competency-based approach in education. *Int. Educ. Stud.* 8:183. doi: 10.5539/ies.v8n8p183
8. Ryan, R. M., and Deci, E. L. (2018). *Self-determination theory*. New York: Guilford Publications.
9. Schunk, D. H. (1991). Self-efficacy and academic motivation. *Educ. Psychol.* 26, 207–231. doi: 10.1080/00461520.1991.9653133
10. Steinmayr, R., Weidinger, A. F., Schwinger, M., and Spinath, B. (2019). The importance of students’ motivation for their academic achievement – replicating and extending previous findings. *Front. Psychol.* 10:1730. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01730
11. Weiner, B. (1985). An attributional theory of achievement motivation and emotion. *Psychol. Rev.* 92, 548–573. doi: 10.1037/0033-295x.92.4.548